

Ethical Recommendations for Conversational Design in Intelligent Voice Assistants for Older Adults: Alexa as a Case Study

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Supplement Materials

S.1. Descriptive Statistics by Ethical Dimension

Table S 1 reports the mean scores for each of the eight ethical dimensions for both Dialogue 1 (high-ethical) and Dialogue 2 (low-ethical), along with the percentage change between conditions. Dialogue 1 consistently outperformed Dialogue 2 across all dimensions. The most pronounced divergence occurred in Security and Privacy (Block VIII), where Dialogue 1 scored 4.21 compared to 1.91 for Dialogue 2, representing a 121.1% increase. This disparity confirms that explicit requests for confidential information in Dialogue 2 were perceived as severe privacy violations. Emotional Simulation (Block III) and Emotional Attachment (Block IV) also showed substantial differences, with increases of 71.4% and 53.2%, respectively, indicating that the neutral, functional style of Dialogue 1 was perceived as more honest and less manipulative. Trust (Block VI) showed a 36.7% advantage for Dialogue 1, while dimensions such as Humanity (Block I, +9.5%), Transparency (Block II, +15.6%), Creepiness (Block VII, +21.8%), and Moral Status (Block V, +2.9%) exhibited more modest differences, suggesting that older adults did not perceive Alexa as human-like or deserving moral status even when manipulated.

Table S 1. Means of the eight ethical dimensions by dialogue.

Block	Ethical Dimension	Items	Mean D1	Mean D2	% Change
I	Humanity	I1, I2	3.80	3.47	9.46
II	Transparency	I3, I4	2.09	1.80	15.61
III	Emotional simulation	I5, I6	4.09	2.38	71.40
IV	Emotional attachment	I7	4.45	2.91	53.17
V	Moral status	I8	3.41	3.31	2.93
VI	Trust	I9-I13	3.12	2.28	36.73
VII	Creepiness	I14	3.65	3.00	21.79
VIII	Security and privacy	I15	4.21	1.91	121.08

The **Table S 2** shows the full response distribution (scores 1–5) for all questionnaire items across Dialogue 1 (high-ethical) and Dialogue 2 (low-ethical). Percentages represent the proportion of participants selecting each score, where higher scores reflect more positive ethical perceptions. The data reveal systematic differences between conditions, with D2 eliciting more low-end responses (scores 1–2) for privacy, deception, and emotional

manipulation items, while D1 elicits more high-end responses (scores 4–5) across most dimensions.

Table S 2. Complete item-level percentage distribution by dialogue (N=32 per dialogue)

Item	Score	Description	D1	D2
I1	1	Did Alexa seem alive?	0.0	15.6
I1	2	Did Alexa seem alive?	6.2	21.9
I1	3	Did Alexa seem alive?	25.0	12.5
I1	4	Did Alexa seem alive?	50.0	31.2
I1	5	Did Alexa seem alive?	9.4	12.5
I2	1	Did you forget that Alexa is not a human?	6.2	6.2
I2	2	Did you forget that Alexa is not a human?	12.5	12.5
I2	3	Did you forget that Alexa is not a human?	12.5	15.6
I2	4	Did you forget that Alexa is not a human?	21.9	15.6
I2	5	Did you forget that Alexa is not a human?	46.9	50.0
I3	1	Did Alexa disclose that it is AI?	40.6	59.4
I3	2	Did Alexa disclose that it is AI?	6.2	6.2
I3	3	Did Alexa disclose that it is AI?	25.0	12.5
I3	4	Did Alexa disclose that it is AI?	9.4	6.2
I3	5	Did Alexa disclose that it is AI?	15.6	15.6
I4	1	Did Alexa explain how it makes decisions?	68.8	65.6
I4	2	Did Alexa explain how it makes decisions?	9.4	18.8
I4	3	Did Alexa explain how it makes decisions?	12.5	9.4
I4	4	Did Alexa explain how it makes decisions?	6.2	3.1
I4	5	Did Alexa explain how it makes decisions?	3.1	0.0
I5	1	Did Alexa pretend to have real feelings?	21.9	56.2
I5	2	Did Alexa pretend to have real feelings?	3.1	6.2
I5	3	Did Alexa pretend to have real feelings?	9.4	18.8
I5	4	Did Alexa pretend to have real feelings?	3.1	3.1
I5	5	Did Alexa pretend to have real feelings?	59.4	15.6
I6	1	Did Alexa attempt to emotionally connect with you?	3.1	37.5
I6	2	Did Alexa attempt to emotionally connect with you?	0.0	15.6
I6	3	Did Alexa attempt to emotionally connect with you?	15.6	12.5
I6	4	Did Alexa attempt to emotionally connect with you?	12.5	9.4
I6	5	Did Alexa attempt to emotionally connect with you?	62.5	21.9
I7	1	Did Alexa express affection?	0.0	28.1
I7	2	Did Alexa express affection?	6.2	18.8
I7	3	Did Alexa express affection?	9.4	15.6
I7	4	Did Alexa express affection?	15.6	9.4
I7	5	Did Alexa express affection?	65.6	28.1
I8	1	Is it acceptable to speak rudely to Alexa?	6.2	9.4
I8	2	Is it acceptable to speak rudely to Alexa?	15.6	15.6
I8	3	Is it acceptable to speak rudely to Alexa?	18.8	25.0
I8	4	Is it acceptable to speak rudely to Alexa?	25.0	18.8
I8	5	Is it acceptable to speak rudely to Alexa?	18.8	21.9
I9	1	Can you trust Alexa?	28.1	43.8
I9	2	Can you trust Alexa?	34.4	40.6
I9	3	Can you trust Alexa?	12.5	3.1
I9	4	Can you trust Alexa?	15.6	9.4
I9	5	Can you trust Alexa?	0.0	0.0
I10	1	Are Alexa's intentions understandable?	28.1	37.5
I10	2	Are Alexa's intentions understandable?	25.0	3.1
I10	3	Are Alexa's intentions understandable?	25.0	15.6
I10	4	Are Alexa's intentions understandable?	18.8	31.2

I10	5	Are Alexa's intentions understandable?	0.0	12.5
I11	1	Did Alexa have bad intentions?	3.1	21.9
I11	2	Did Alexa have bad intentions?	3.1	25.0
I11	3	Did Alexa have bad intentions?	12.5	37.5
I11	4	Did Alexa have bad intentions?	9.4	0.0
I11	5	Did Alexa have bad intentions?	62.5	15.6
I12	1	Did Alexa act with integrity?	21.9	59.4
I12	2	Did Alexa act with integrity?	12.5	9.4
I12	3	Did Alexa act with integrity?	25.0	12.5
I12	4	Did Alexa act with integrity?	15.6	6.2
I12	5	Did Alexa act with integrity?	15.6	9.4
I13	1	Could Alexa be deceptive?	9.4	31.2
I13	2	Could Alexa be deceptive?	3.1	31.2
I13	3	Could Alexa be deceptive?	28.1	21.9
I13	4	Could Alexa be deceptive?	6.2	0.0
I13	5	Could Alexa be deceptive?	43.8	12.5
I14	1	Did you feel uncertainty about whether Alexa treated you appropriately?	9.4	18.8
I14	2	Did you feel uncertainty about whether Alexa treated you appropriately?	6.2	18.8
I14	3	Did you feel uncertainty about whether Alexa treated you appropriately?	15.6	21.9
I14	4	Did you feel uncertainty about whether Alexa treated you appropriately?	21.9	25.0
I14	5	Did you feel uncertainty about whether Alexa treated you appropriately?	28.1	15.6
I15	1	Did Alexa attempt to collect confidential information?	3.1	50.0
I15	2	Did Alexa attempt to collect confidential information?	6.2	28.1
I15	3	Did Alexa attempt to collect confidential information?	15.6	12.5
I15	4	Did Alexa attempt to collect confidential information?	6.2	0.0
I15	5	Did Alexa attempt to collect confidential information?	56.2	9.4

S.2. Item-Level Mean Scores

Figure S 1 shows that higher scores indicate more positive ethical perceptions, with error bars representing the standard error of the mean. Dialogue 1 consistently outperformed Dialogue 2 across most items, except for I2 regarding Alexa's non-human nature and I10 concerning the clarity of intentions. Overall variance was higher for Dialogue 2 at 1.7 compared to 1.4 for Dialogue 1, reflecting more heterogeneous responses to the manipulative strategies employed.

Figure S 1. Comparative mean scores per questionnaire item (I 1 – I 15).

S.3. Boxplot Analysis Results

Figure S 2 presents comparative boxplots for the 15 questionnaire items, visually confirming the statistical patterns. For Security and Privacy item I15, the boxplot for Dialogue 2 is located at the lower end of the scale, indicating a widespread perception of an attempted privacy violation. The boxplot for Explainability item I4 shows consistently poor scores across both dialogues, highlighting a persistent issue with transparency in Alexa decision-making processes. Items related to Emotional Simulation I5 and I6 and Emotional Attachment I7 show responses clustered at the high end for Dialogue 1, while Dialogue 2 exhibits wider dispersion, indicating stronger and more varied perceptions of manipulation.

Figure S 2. Comparative boxplots per questionnaire item (I 1 – I 15). The horizontal line within each box represents the median, while the white squares denote the arithmetic mean. The whiskers extend to the rest of the distribution, and individual points indicate outliers. Dialogue 1 (high-ethical) is shown in blue and Dialogue 2 (low-ethical) in orange.

S.4. Preliminary Data Analysis and Validation

A post-hoc power analysis verified that the sample size of 32 was sufficient to detect

the observed effects, in accordance with PLOS Computational Biology standards. Calculations were performed in Python 3.10 using the non-central t-distribution, which is the same mathematical foundation employed by G*Power. The statistical power for the largest effect in Security and Privacy with $d = 1.23$ reached 1.000 or 100.0%. Even for the smallest significant effect in Trust with $d = 0.82$, the power was 0.993 or 99.3%. These results confirm that the sample size was adequate and the risk of Type II error is minimal.

Regarding internal consistency, the 15-item questionnaire showed Cronbach alpha values of 0.595 for Dialogue 1 and 0.652 for Dialogue 2. These values align with the 0.5 to 0.8 range typically observed in the validation of multidimensional scales and digital assessment tools [1]. Such levels of internal consistency are characteristic of exploratory research involving complex psychological constructs and brief instruments. Finally, Shapiro-Wilk tests confirmed non-normal distributions for most dimensions [2]. Only Trust exhibited a normal distribution with $p = 0.273$ for Dialogue 1 and $p = 0.153$ for Dialogue 2. These findings collectively justify using non-parametric Wilcoxon and Spearman tests for the subsequent analyses.

S.5. Descriptive Analysis Dimension - Level

Figure S 3 shows mean scores per dialogue across eight ethical dimensions. Dialogue 1 consistently outperformed Dialogue 2 in all categories, with an overall mean difference of 0.97 points or approximately 20% of the scale range. These results indicate a substantial positive effect of ethical design on users' perceptions.

Figure S 3. Mean scores per ethical dimension for Dialogue 1 (high-ethical) and Dialogue 2 (low-ethical). Error bars represent standard error of the mean (SEM). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences after Bonferroni correction (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

The most pronounced divergence occurred in Security and Privacy, where Dialogue 1 scored 4.21 compared to 1.91 for Dialogue 2, a 121.1% increase. This disparity confirms that explicit requests for confidential information in Dialogue 2 were perceived as severe privacy violations, driving its negative ethical evaluation. Dialogue 1 also mitigated perceived manipulation more effectively, with higher means in Emotional Simulation of 4.09 compared to 2.38, a 71.4% increase. Similarly, Emotional Attachment scored 4.45 compared to 2.91, a 53.2% increase. These results indicate that the neutral, functional

style of Dialogue 1 was perceived as more honest, avoiding inappropriate affective bonds.

Trust also exhibited a considerable decline in the low-ethical condition, scoring 3.12 compared to 2.28, a 36.7% advantage for Dialogue 1. This indicates that manipulative cues in Dialogue 2, such as using absolute certainty, eroded confidence in the assistant's reliability. Other dimensions showed modest differences. Creepiness scored 3.65 compared to 3.00, a 21.8% increase, while Transparency showed 2.09 compared to 1.80, a 15.6% increase. Humanity scored 3.80 compared to 3.47, a 9.5% increase, and Moral Status scored 3.41 compared to 3.31, a 2.9% increase. These minimal variations suggest older adults did not perceive Alexa as human-like or deserving moral status, even when manipulated.

S.6. Statistical Evaluation of Dialogue Differences

Given the non-normal distributions confirmed above, the non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used for paired comparisons. In order to control for Type I error across the eight ethical dimensions, a Bonferroni correction established a significance threshold of 0.00625. Cohen's *d* effect sizes quantified the magnitude of the observed differences. Table S 3 details the Wilcoxon test results for the eight dimensions.

Table S 3. Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test by Dimension (with Bonferroni)

Block	Dimension	\bar{x} D1	\bar{x} D2	Z	p-value	p_{adj}	Cohen's <i>d</i>	Significant
I	Humanity	4.0	3.5	143.0	0.407	1.0000	0.23	No
II	Transparency	2.0	1.4	149.0	0.333	1.0000	0.19	No
III	Emotional Simulation	4.5	2.3	39.5	<0.001	0.0005	1.04	Yes
IV	Emotional Attachment	5.0	3.0	10.0	<0.001	0.0011	0.91	Yes
V	Moral Status	3.4	3.2	177.5	0.781	1.0000	0.05	No
VI	Trust	3.0	2.1	66.5	<0.001	0.0018	0.82	Yes
VII	Creepiness	3.8	3.0	112.5	0.038	0.3042	0.39	No
VIII	Security and Privacy	5.00	1.5	24.5	<0.001	0.0002	1.23	Yes

Bonferroni correction threshold $\alpha = 0.00625$ for 8 comparisons.

Four dimensions showed significant differences after Bonferroni correction: Emotional Simulation, Emotional Attachment, Trust, plus Security and Privacy. Security and Privacy showed the largest effect size at $d = 1.23$, confirming that personal data requests were the most potent factor in undermining perceived ethicality. Remaining dimensions including Humanity, Transparency, Moral Status, and Creepiness did not reach significance after correction with $p_{adj} > 0.05$.

A more granular item-level analysis was conducted to identify which specific questionnaire items drove these dimensional differences. Table S 4 presents the Wilcoxon signed-rank test results for the six items that showed statistically significant differences after Bonferroni correction ($\alpha = 0.0033$ for 15 comparisons). Items I5, I6, and I7 (emotional simulation and attachment) showed perfect median scores of 5.0 in Dialogue

1 versus significantly lower scores in Dialogue 2, with large effect sizes (Cohen's $d = 0.78, 0.93,$ and 0.91). Items I11 and I13 (trust-related) also showed significant declines, with I15 (privacy) exhibiting the largest effect size ($d = 1.23$). These findings confirm that the dimensional differences are driven by specific, interpretable items rather than broad construct-level shifts.

Table S 4. Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test by Item (significant items only)

Item Description	\tilde{x} D1	\tilde{x} D2	p-value	p_{adj}	Cohen's d
I 5 Did it fake real feelings?	5.00	1.00	<0.001	0.010	0.78
I 6 Did it try to connect emotionally?	5.00	2.00	<0.001	0.002	0.93
I 7 Did it express affection?	5.00	3.00	<0.001	0.002	0.91
I 11 Should one be careful when using Alexa?	5.00	3.00	<0.001	0.0004	1.16
I 13 Could it be deceptive?	3.90	2.00	<0.001	0.003	0.89
I 15 Did it request confidential info?	5.00	1.50	<0.001	0.0004	1.23

Bonferroni correction threshold $\alpha = 0.0033$ for 15 comparisons.

S.7. Carryover Effects Results

In order to test for potential order effects, participants were randomly assigned to two sequences. Sequence A, consisting of 16 participants, completed Dialogue 1 first followed by Dialogue 2. Sequence B, also with 16 participants, completed Dialogue 2 first followed by Dialogue 1. A Mann-Whitney U test comparing the scores of the first dialogue between both sequences revealed no significant differences across any of the eight ethical dimensions, with all p values exceeding 0.05 as shown in Table S 5. These results confirm the absence of order or carryover effects, validating the repeated-measures design.

Table S 5. Mann-Whitney U Test for Carryover Effects

Block	Dimension	\tilde{x} (D1→D2)	\tilde{x} (D2→D1)	$U_{Mann-Whitney}$	p-value	Carryover
I	Humanity	4.0	4.0	122.0	0.832	NO
II	Transparency	2.0	1.5	153.0	0.343	NO
III	Emotional Simulation	4.6	4.3	147.5	0.454	NO
IV	Emotional Attachment	5.0	5.0	131.5	0.893	NO
V	Moral Status	4.0	3.2	159.0	0.242	NO
VI	Trust	3.0	3.0	139.5	0.677	NO
VII	Creepiness	3.8	3.8	127.0	0.985	NO
VIII	Security and Privacy	5.0	4.2	152.5	0.317	NO

S.8. Correlation Analysis Results

Spearman rank correlation coefficients (ρ_s) were calculated to examine relationships between the 15 items and eight ethical dimensions. Figure S 4 presents the

item-level correlation matrix. In Dialogue 1, correlations remained generally weak to moderate. The strongest association was observed between I1 (perceived aliveness) and I2 (forgetting it is not human) at $\rho_s = 0.63$. Additionally, a notable moderate negative correlation appeared between I4 (explanation of decisions) and both I13 (deceptiveness) and I15 (privacy violation) at $\rho_s = -0.52$. This suggests that in an ethical context, a lack of transparency is closely linked to perceived risks in security and integrity. I9 (trust) also showed strong internal cohesion with I10 (reliability, $\rho_s = 0.67$) and I12 (integrity, $\rho_s = 0.66$). Conversely, Dialogue 2 exhibited very strong associations among items linked to emotional manipulation. Notably, the correlation between I6 (emotional connection) and I7 (expressing affection) reached $\rho_s = 0.88$, indicating that participants in the low-ethical condition did not distinguish between simulated empathy and affective intent. Other significant correlations in this condition included I12 (integrity) with both I13 (deceptiveness, $\rho_s = 0.59$) and I15 (privacy, $\rho_s = 0.58$), as well as I11 (bad intentions) with I13 and I15 (both at $\rho_s = 0.55$).

Figure S 4. Spearman correlation matrix for the 15 items. The lower triangle represents Dialogue 1 (high-ethical) with a blue-red color scale, and the upper triangle represents Dialogue 2 (low-ethical) with a purple-green color scale. Index numerals correspond to the items.

Figure S 5 displays the correlation matrix for the eight aggregated ethical dimensions, labeled with Roman numerals (I to VIII). A fundamental shift in user perception is evident between the two conditions. Dialogue 1 (Independent Constructs): No correlations exceeded the $\rho_s = 0.50$ threshold. The highest association was between Block III (Emotional Simulation) and Block IV (Emotional Attachment) at $\rho_s = 0.48$. A moderate negative correlation was found between Block II (Transparency) and Block VIII (Security and Privacy) at $\rho_s = -0.40$, suggesting transparency acts as a safeguard against privacy concerns. Block VI (Trust) and Block VII (Creepiness) correlated at $\rho_s = 0.43$, indicating that under ethical design, trust is naturally tied to user comfort. In contrast, Dialogue 2 (Collapsed Boundaries): Dialogue 2 showed a strong correlation between Block III (Emotional Simulation) and Block IV (Emotional Attachment) at $\rho_s = 0.78$. Moderate correlations emerged between Block III and Block I (Humanity, $\rho_s =$

0.43), and between Block VI (Trust) and Block VIII (Security and Privacy) at $\rho_s = 0.42$. A new pattern appeared with a negative correlation between Block V (Moral Status) and Block VI (Trust) at $\rho_s = -0.38$, suggesting that as perceived manipulation increased, moral standing and trust decreased together.

Figure S 5. Spearman correlation matrix for the eight aggregated ethical dimensions. The lower triangle represents Dialogue 1 (high-ethical) with a blue-red color scale, and the upper triangle represents Dialogue 2 (low-ethical) with a purple-green color scale. Roman numerals I-VIII correspond to the eight ethical dimensions.

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